

PROTOCOL FOR HIGH HORIZONS POPULATION- LEVEL HEAT-HEALTH IMPACTS STUDY IN GREECE, ITALY, KENYA, SOUTH AFRICA, AND SWEDEN

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VERSION 1.2; MAY 2024

HIGH Horizons consortium

Suggested citation

Part C, Brimicombe C, Roos N. Protocol for HIGH Horizons Population-Level Heat-Health Impacts Study in Greece, Italy, Kenya, South Africa, and Sweden. Zenodo; 2024. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10947994. License CC BY4.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ANC	Antenatal care
AT	Apparent Temperature
BMI	Body Mass Index
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CNN	Convolutional Neural Net
DEP-Lazio	Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service, ASL Roma 1
DLNM	Distributed lag nonlinear model
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
ERA5	The 5th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCW	Health care worker
HDSS	Health and Demographic Surveillance System
HIC	High income country
HIV/AIDS	Human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LMIC	Low and middle income country
LMP	Last menstrual period
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
NICU	Neonatal intensive care unit
PNC	Postnatal care
SA	South Africa
SPR	Swedish Pregnancy Register
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index (a thermal comfort index)
UK	United Kingdom
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
UNI GRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)
WBGT	Wet-bulb globe temperature
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

Study synopsis

Rationale: The frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme weather events, including heatwaves, have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising. Accumulating epidemiological evidence shows an increased risk of adverse health outcomes for pregnant women, newborns, and young children associated with exposure to extreme heat and high ambient temperatures. There is also some evidence to suggest that heat exposure during gestation has long-term health consequences for the child. This study forms part of the larger HIGH Horizons project, focussed on the impacts of climate change, and specifically heat, on maternal, neonatal and child health (MNCH). The study will inform the selection of heat-related indicators for monitoring and surveillance purposes, development of meaningful heat thresholds, and the design and implementation of a personalised Early Warning System.

Importantly, the study is designed to understand the relationships between heat exposure and health outcomes during pregnancy, the postpartum and neonatal periods, as well as early childhood. The study will be conducted in multiple countries, varying in climate zones and socio-economic characteristics, which will increase international representation and generalisability.

Objectives:

Primary objectives:

- 1) To quantify relationships between ambient temperature exposures and risk of adverse maternal, neonatal, and child health outcomes;
- 2) To identify the relative temperature threshold(s) above which risk of an adverse outcome is increased;
- 3) To determine valid and reliable heat indicators for assessing heat-MNCH impacts at population-level;
- 4) To characterise groups of pregnant women and children at high risk of heat-related conditions;

- 5) To determine if heat-MNCH associations vary by location, climate, facility, or quality of care, as the data allow.

Secondary objectives:

- 6) To identify critical windows of susceptibility during gestation or during infancy and childhood;
- 7) To explore impacts of both acute and cumulative heat exposures.

Study design: The study will follow a time-series approach to assess the impacts of high environmental temperature and heat stress on adverse MNCH outcomes. The study is observational (non-interventional), using data from secondary sources only. No primary data will be collected.

Methods: Maternal, perinatal and neonatal health data from different registries and cohorts will be used across different settings and population characteristics. Daily time-series of exposures (such as minimum, mean, and maximum temperatures, universal thermal climate index, wet-bulb globe temperature, apparent temperature, and relative humidity) have been constructed from hourly openly available reanalysis data, obtained from the Copernicus Climate Data Store or other relevant data repository for each country. Daily exposures will be linked with MNCH outcomes in time and space, including varying lag structures. We will employ a range of complementary analytical approaches, including time-series regression, time-stratified case-crossover, and time-to-event analyses to model associations between environmental exposures and MNCH outcomes.

Ethical considerations: All partners will obtain approval from relevant ethics committees in countries where the data originate and where data analyses will take place. The data will be anonymized, and results will be presented in aggregated format so that individuals will not be identifiable.

Dissemination: Outputs from this study will be presented at different international scientific fora for maternal, neonatal and child health as well as climate change. Scientific evidence generated from the project will be published in

scientific peer reviewed articles. Additionally, results will be disseminated among local, provincial and national government officials, advocacy groups, and researchers to support policy changes.

Funding acknowledgments: Research that will be conducted in this study is supported by the European Union (EU) under the Environmental and Health Call (Award number: 101057843) under the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027). Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK (Reference number: 10038478).

1 Study rationale

1.1 Context

Like all other regions of the world, Europe and Africa have experienced changes in precipitation and temperature over the past four decades as a result of anthropogenic climate change. Temperatures are rising (Gebrechorkos et al., 2019, Almazroui et al., 2020, Fitzpatrick et al., 2020, IPCC, 2021), and extreme heat events are increasing in frequency and intensity (Ceccherini et al., 2017). It is estimated that 48-74% of the global population will be exposed to more than 20 days of deadly heat per year by 2100 (Mora et al., 2017). Africa has been shown to be particularly vulnerable to climate change and extreme heat events because of poverty, poor sanitation, high prevalence of malnutrition, infections, non-communicable diseases, poor quality housing and weak, non-resilient health care systems.

A series of systematic reviews by members of the HIGH Horizons team identified in excess of 200 studies demonstrating the harmful direct impacts of heat on maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) outcomes, including preterm birth, stillbirth, congenital anomalies, preeclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, foetal distress and long-term impacts on children's health (Chersich et al., 2020, Haghighi et al., 2021, Chersich M et al., 2021). Almost all of these studies were conducted in high-income countries (HICs), leaving no doubt that concerns around heat exposure and adverse MNCH outcomes will not be confined to contexts in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). In fact, effect sizes in sub-Saharan Africa may be even larger than in HICs, the majority of which have temperate climates, growing air conditioning penetrance, and heat-resistant housing. Large parts of sub-Saharan Africa have none of those protective features. Another systematic review by the team (unpublished) located 120 studies documenting the negative effects of extreme heat exposure in children under two years. These first years of life are a unique period of vulnerability – but also a window of opportunity – when

the foundations of optimum health, growth, and neurodevelopment across the lifespan are established. A real limitation to date is the lack of research on the impacts of extreme heat throughout pregnancy and a sparse literature base for the African continent and parts of the tropics (MacVicar et al., 2017; Syed et al., 2022).

Good maternal health is crucial for successful birth and neonatal outcomes and requires screening, diagnosing and disease prevention of important conditions that may impact pregnancy. Threats to maternal and perinatal health include short time intervals between pregnancies, unmet nutritional needs, infections, heavy physical labour and underlying chronic conditions like diabetes and obesity, which in turn may complicate pregnancy outcomes, further exacerbated by climate change (Roos et al., 2021). Exposure to high temperatures during pregnancy has a range of physiological effects, including a reduction in placental blood flow due to vasodilation (Wang et al., 2020), and an inflammatory response that may trigger early labour (Samuels et al., 2022). We have found that high ambient temperatures in early pregnancy increase the risk of severe hypertensive disorders (preeclampsia, eclampsia, and HELLP syndrome), supporting the hypothesis that heat exposure in early pregnancy impairs early placental development (Part et al., 2022).

Women and neonates are among the most vulnerable groups across a range of social and cultural contexts. Identifying pregnant women and neonates as at-risk groups during climate-related events, such as heat extremes, is becoming an emerging need for an adequate policy and public health response to mitigate the risk of heat on adverse MNCH outcomes. Heat exposure and vulnerability to impacts vary widely across geographical areas, population groups, and by socio-economic status. Designing effective climate policies depends on rigorous quantification and monitoring of heat-related impacts among the most vulnerable, highest-risk groups. Research is required to assess and quantify the

differential impacts across settings of climate change and heatwaves on MNCH outcomes. This is particularly needed in low- and middle-income countries where the burden is likely to be the largest and likely to increase over time and in areas with the poorest resources to adapt.

While it is clear that pregnant and postpartum women and infants are heavily affected by climate change, these populations have received little attention to date in climate change policies and public health responses. Health conditions affecting pregnant and postpartum women, fetuses and infants can have lifelong and trans-generational implications, considerably more profound than among other population groups. Understanding and measuring heat impacts in these populations is thus essential for calculating the overall burden of heat-related disease, and for guiding policy choices.

While there is evidence to support pregnant women, infants, and children being vulnerable groups to extreme heat (Roos N et al., 2021, Dalugoda et al., 2022), there is considerable heterogeneity in the analytical methodologies, exposure metrics, and windows of susceptibility examined in the current literature base, which limits synthesis and comparability of findings across studies and contexts. Research to date has primarily focused on mean air temperature as the environmental exposure of interest. However, mean air temperature does not adequately capture the level of heat stress that a population is exposed to and other environmental exposures (including humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation) should also be taken into account in order to identify meaningful heat thresholds that will inform ENSs to reduce the impacts of heat exposure on MNCH. Heat stress indices are a current methodological approach for improving the accuracy of considering the burden of heat on the body. They include: (i) the Universal Thermal Climate Index, developed as part of a COST action (Fiala et al., 2012, Bröde et al., 2012); (ii) Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT), the current international standard for considering the effects of heat stress on occupational

health (ISO, 2017); and apparent temperature, an empirical approximation of the combined effects of air temperature and relative humidity on a human (Steadman, 1984).

There is a lack of monitoring, warning and policy that targets pregnant and postpartum women and infants at all levels, from international to local level (Rowland, 2008; Smith, 2019). **It is essential that comparable cross-country analyses are carried out to assess the impacts of extreme heat on the health of these vulnerable groups, including the burden of heat-related disease, to support evidence-based policy making and the implementation of tracking and interventions.**

1.2 Description of the overarching HIGH Horizons project

The work outlined in this protocol is part of a larger project looking at the impacts of heat and climate change on maternal, neonatal and child health. The four-year (2022-2026) HIGH Horizons project involves seven partners in Europe, three in Africa, and the World Health Organisation (WHO).

The project centres on vulnerable populations affected by climate change: pregnant and postpartum women, infants, and health workers (<https://www.high-horizons.eu/>).

HIGH Horizons is funded by the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478.

The broader HIGH Horizons project has six main components organised as work packages (WPs), each with specific tasks (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Outline of the HIGH Horizons project organised according to work packages

The WPs/tasks serve to achieve five project objectives (see Figure 1):

1. Identify and select suitable indicators for quantifying and monitoring global, EU, and national-level health impacts of extreme heat.
2. Develop and test an Early Warning Systems (EWS) using a smartphone app to provide individualized and locally adapted heat stress warnings.
3. Identify cost-effective, integrated adaptation-mitigation interventions to alleviate heat impacts on health care workers (HCWs, and to reduce carbon emissions associated with health care.), and to reduce carbon emissions associated with health care.
4. Support global and EU climate policies and activities on the monitoring of direct and indirect impacts of climate change on health, and the strengthening of Early Warning Systems through guidance documents, and risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis.
5. Investigate the biological and thermal physiological pathways from heat effects on adverse health outcomes among pregnant women and their infants in the first year of life.

1.3 Contribution of this sub-study to HIGH Horizons

This study protocol falls within WP2 of HIGH Horizons (assessment of health impacts and facilities), task 2.1 (population-level impacts: measurement).

Analyses of heat-health impacts and data science predictive modelling using population-level data from Sweden, Italy (Lazio region), Greece and data from health facilities in Kenya and South Africa (Gauteng province) underpin all other activities in HIGH Horizons. These analyses, along with systematic reviews, will inform testing and selection of global, EU and national indicators. Analyses will also inform cut-off thresholds for an Early Warning System (EWS), whereby a smartphone app (ClimApp-MCH) will deliver personalised warnings and context-specific messages, co-designed locally.

1.4 Aim and study objectives

The aim of the epidemiological study is to generate evidence to inform the testing and selection of global, EU and national indicators of heat exposure on maternal, neonatal, and child health (MNCH), and to inform cut-off thresholds for a personalised early warning system for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and health workers.

The *primary objectives* of this study are:

- 1) To quantify relationships between ambient temperature exposures and risk of adverse maternal, neonatal, and child health outcomes;
- 2) To identify the relative temperature threshold(s) above which risk of an adverse outcome is increased;
- 3) To determine valid and reliable heat indicators for assessing heat-MNCH impacts at population-level;
- 4) To characterise groups of pregnant women and children at high risk of heat-related conditions;
- 5) To determine if heat-MNCH associations vary by location, climate, facility, or quality of care, as the data allow.

Our *secondary objectives* are:

- 6) To identify critical windows of susceptibility during gestation or during infancy and childhood;
- 7) To explore impacts of both acute and cumulative heat exposures.

2 Methods

HIGH Horizons has access to national, regional and facility health datasets in Europe (Greece, Italy and Sweden) and Africa (Kenya and South Africa).

2.1 Study design

This study is observational (non-interventional), using data from secondary sources only. No primary data will be collected. All outcomes have already occurred; data on which were collected in electronic form within the country of origin. Collection of data in electronic form occurred either as part of routine care procedures (Rome, Sweden, or Greece), or data were extracted from paper-based records as part of research or surveillance activities (South Africa and Kenya). For child health outcomes longitudinal data will be collected from the Health and Demographic Surveillance Systems (HDSS) through the INDEPTH network, and other data sets which are available openly or through data sharing agreements. We will employ a range of complementary analytical approaches and specific study designs, including time-series and time-stratified case-crossover designs as well as time-to-event techniques, to define the significance value where possible of effect estimates and heat thresholds. The choice of approach will depend on factors such as the outcome, number of cases, availability of data on individual-level confounders, and the exposure window of interest.

The study design allows us to use all available data that meet our inclusion criteria. In the event of rare outcomes for which we do not have adequate statistical power, we will consider evidence-based composite outcomes shown to have a similar biological mechanism. An example is grouping stillbirths and neonatal mortality.

2.2 Country climate description

Greece:

Greece is a high-income country and is located in the southernmost part of the Balkan Peninsula. The Greek mainland covers approximately 80% of the total land area while the country and the rest are covered by more than 3000 islands. Significant geographical variations in climate conditions are observed between coastal areas/islands, inland areas and mountainous areas. Greece exhibits a typical Mediterranean climate characterized by mild and wet winters in the

southern lowland and island regions, and colder winters and snowfall in the northern mountainous areas. During winter, mean minimum temperatures range from 5 to 10°C near the coast and from 0 to 5°C over the mainland, while temperatures below 0 ° C are recorded in mountainous areas. From June to August, rainfall is infrequent, and dry conditions prevail, with mean maximum temperatures ranging between 29 and 35°C (Giannakopoulos, 2011).

Italy:

Italy is a high-income country. Italy has a predominantly Mediterranean climate with mild (sometimes rainy) winters, and hot dry summers. Lazio (Italy) in general has a hot climate. Temperatures during the day are in the range from 12°C (54 °F) in January to 30°C (86 °F) in August. The driest month is July with just 3 days of rain, and the wettest month is November with 12 days of rain.

Sweden:

Sweden is a high-income country. Sweden's proximity to the North Atlantic and prevailing south-westerly to westerly winds result in a climate that is mild in the winter months, but the northernmost part of the country has a sub-Arctic climate with long, cold and snowy winters. There are three different climatic zones in Sweden: the south has an oceanic climate, the centre has a humid continental climate, and the north has a subarctic climate. Summers in the south and centre of Sweden are warm and pleasant, with average high temperatures ranging between 20°C and 25°C.

Kenya:

Kenya is a lower-middle income country. The region of Mombasa has a tropical climate, with temperatures ranging from 21°C to 32°C and average annual rainfall ranging from 300mm to 1200mm (Weatherspark, n.d.). This area experiences seasonal changes in precipitation and temperatures, which could affect the spread of infectious diseases (Fares, 2013).

South Africa:

South Africa is an upper-middle income country. Johannesburg and Soweto are in the Gauteng province, which is the smallest and most densely populated province in the country. Johannesburg is the provincial capital of Gauteng and the largest city in South Africa, with approximately 5 million inhabitants (Statistics South Africa, 2018). Soweto is a low-income urban settlement to the west of Johannesburg. The catchment area of Soweto study facilities has a population of approximately 1.7 million. The province has a temperate climate with four distinct seasons: Summer (December to February), autumn (March to May), winter (June to August), and spring (September to November). Average daily temperatures range from 15°C to 28°C during the summer, and from 7°C to 18°C during the winter (Part et al., 2022). Winter is the driest season with the highest rainfall in summer.

2.3 MNCH data

Here, an outline of the Maternal, Newborn and Child Health datasets used for analysis in the HIGH Horizons project is presented.

Table 1. Overview of data coverage in the selected countries and regions

Country	Coverage	Time period	Number of births
Greece	Nationwide	1999-2021	2,316,655
Italy	Regional (Lazio)	2001-2019	857,145
Sweden	Nationwide	2014-2021	560,615
Kenya	Facility (N=1)	2017-2022	3212
South Africa	Facility (N=11)	2016-2023	220,000
South Africa	Facility (N=1); birth surveillance data	2017-2018	8503

2.3.1 Greece

➤ Birth data

The dataset contains information on 2,316,655 births in Greece from 1999 to 2021. Variables concerning each birth include i) stillbirth, ii) cause of stillbirth, iii) person present at birth, iv) gestational weeks v) birth weight in grams, vi) maternal age,

vii) mode of delivery, viii) maternal nationality, ix) marital status, x) residence (urban/rural/semi urban), xi) number of newborns. The full date of childbirth (DD/MM/YY) and the municipality of residence of the mother is available for all births. Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) is the owner of the data.

➤ **Hospitalization data**

Nationwide data on hospitalizations of pregnant women from 1999-2015 will be used. The dataset will contain geographically aggregated data on hospitalisation per ICD code falling into the “Pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium” category (1999-2012: ICD-9, 2014-2015: ICD-10). Similarly, data on hospitalizations of children up to 1 year of age will be acquired.

2.3.2 Italy

Italian data (for the Lazio Region only) are property of the Lazio Region and will be analysed by the Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service – ASL Roma 1 (hereafter DEP-Lazio). The Certificate of Delivery Care Registry of the Lazio Region (one of the 20 Italian regions, the one where Rome is located) will be used. The database includes births between 2001 and 2019 and a total of about 857,145 births. The regional Register includes information on the type of delivery, clinical status of the baby at birth, and socio-demographic variables of the mother, date of delivery, maternal citizenship, maternal age, educational level, occupational status, municipality of birth, gestational age, birth weight, malformations at birth, singleton or twin delivery, as well as longitude and latitude of residential address. Through the latter, an index is available to characterize the socio-economic status of the maternal residential area. Furthermore, by linking the mother ID to the hospital discharge files or drug prescription files, we can get info about pre-existing or later admissions as well as drug prescriptions of the mother.

2.3.3 Sweden

The Swedish Pregnancy Register (SPR) covers more than 92% of births in Sweden and provides high quality data for research in pregnancy and early childhood as well as quality of care improvement (Stephansson et al., 2018). Data are available from January 1, 2014, to December 31, 2019 and includes 560,615 births. Information on each pregnancy is available from the woman's first visit to antenatal care to their postnatal follow-up visit at around 8-16 weeks postpartum. The majority of data is collected directly from electronic medical records (Stephansson et al., 2018). Each individual in Sweden has a unique identifier assigned at birth or immigration and is used to link the pregnant woman in the SPR with the National Patient Register (for maternal and neonatal health outcomes) (Ludvigsson et al., 2011), and Statistics Sweden for socioeconomic and residential address information (de Bont et al., 2022).

2.3.4 Kenya

The dataset comprises of 3212 births from the Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa and its delivery wards. It covers the period 2017 to 2022. Key outcomes included in this dataset are for example: duration of labour, mother health during labour, mother HIV status, mode of delivery, APGAR score, mode of delivery (including type of caesarean section), birth weight, birth outcome/child condition at birth.

2.3.5 South Africa

➤ Soweto surveillance data

The Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics Research Unit of the University of the Witwatersrand, led by Professor Shabir Madhi, funds and maintains a passive surveillance (birth register) dataset for the Soweto region of South Africa. Information is recorded on all deliveries at midwife-led clinics and tertiary referral hospital in the region (N = 10), including date of admission, date and time of delivery, maternal characteristics (age, parity, gravidity, nationality), morbidities (e.g. maternal HIV status) and complications at birth, number of infants born,

mode of delivery (normal vaginal delivery, caesarean section), assisted delivery (vacuum extraction, forceps), caesarean section (emergency, elective), reason for caesarean section, duration of delivery (HH:MM), gestational age at delivery (completed weeks), birth outcome (live born, fresh stillbirth, macerated stillbirth), infant characteristics (sex, birth weight, head circumference, length), APGAR score at 5 minutes and 10 minutes of life, and condition of the child (transferred to mother, transferred to nursery, died, other). The database includes approximately 220 000 births between April 2016 and March 2023. It is estimated that this dataset includes 98% of births that occurred in Soweto during this period (Statistics South Africa, 2020).

➤ **Inner city Johannesburg birth register data**

Maternal health, demographic, and obstetric history data were collected from birth registries to include all births between 01 July 2017 and 30 June 2018 at one tertiary referral hospital in inner city Johannesburg. Data were originally collected as part of a population-based observational medical record review study, led by collaborators at Wits RHI. Approximately 8500 women deliver in this hospital annually. It serves inner city Johannesburg and surrounding suburban areas, receiving referrals from primary care and secondary level facilities for high-risk deliveries. Information is available for each birth (n=8503), including antepartum complications / reason for referral (e.g. diabetes, preeclampsia, antepartum haemorrhage, prelabour rupture of the membranes), gestational age at delivery, mode of delivery and indication for emergency caesarean section (e.g. foetal distress), duration of labour, postpartum complications (e.g. distress, infection, postpartum haemorrhage), transfer of mother (e.g. to intensive care unit), maternal HIV status, infant status at birth (e.g. alive, intrapartum stillbirth, antepartum stillbirth), birth weight, infant complications (e.g. birth asphyxia, respiratory distress), transfer of infant (e.g. to NICU), APGAR score, congenital anomalies (e.g. hydrocephalus), etc.

2.3.6 Priority health outcomes

For cross-country analyses, we will prioritise MNCH outcomes that are available in all datasets (outlined below), which will enable the comparison of temperature and heat effect estimates across settings. We have also prepared a more extensive list of MNCH outcomes that are available in one or more datasets and which we hypothesise to be affected by heat exposure. In addition to the priority outcomes, individual teams will assess the impacts of high temperature and extreme heat on a range of MNCH outcomes available within their respective datasets.

All health outcome variables must include the full date (DD/MM/YY) of event (i.e. diagnosis or delivery) and location of residence or name of birthing facility to enable linkage with exposure data.

Perinatal health

- *Gestational age at birth*: Completed weeks of gestation at birth (continuous measure) using best estimate available (e.g., last menstrual period (LMP) or second trimester ultrasound for gestational dating).
- *Preterm birth*: Delivery of a live born infant at less than 37 weeks' gestation (based on best estimate – see above).
 - *Moderately preterm*: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 32 and < 37 weeks' gestation.
 - *Very preterm*: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 28 and < 32 weeks' gestation.
 - *Extremely preterm*: Delivery of a live born infant at ≥ 22 and < 28 weeks' gestation.
- *Stillbirth*: Foetal death prior to the complete expulsion of the foetus
 - *Intrapartum (fresh) stillbirth*: Foetal death immediately before or during labour with no signs of maceration (intact skin) after 22 or 28 gestational weeks

- *Antepartum (macerated) stillbirth*: Foetal death before labour with signs of maceration (discolouration and peeling of the skin) after 22 or 28 gestational weeks.
- *Birth weight*: Weight of baby at birth in grams (continuous measure).
- *Low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing less than 2500 grams.
 - *Moderately low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1500 to < 2500 grams.
 - *Very low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 1000 to < 1500 grams.
 - *Extremely low birth weight*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing < 1000 grams.
- *Small for gestational age*: below 10th percentile of birth weight for gestational age and sex (Lawn et al., 2023)
- *Macrosomia*: Delivery of a live born infant weighing ≥ 4500 grams.
- *APGAR score at 5 minutes after birth* (ordinal measure, 1-10).
- *Low APGAR score*: APGAR score of <7 at 5 minutes of age.
- *Interfacility transfer*: Transfer of newborn to neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) or other specialised ward/unit for complication.

Maternal health

- *Mode of delivery*:
 - *Vaginal birth*
 - *Assisted vaginal birth (e.g. by forceps or vacuum extraction)*
 - *Caesarean section (C-section)*
 - *Any C-section*
 - *Emergency C-section*
 - *Elective C-section*
- *Duration of labour* (HH:MM)
- *Interfacility transfer*: Transfer of woman to intensive care unit (ICU) or other specialised ward/unit for complication.

Child health

- *Hospitalisation*: Admission to hospital, all cause
- *Mortality*
 - *Neonatal mortality*: born alive with death (all cause) between 0-28 days.
 - *Infant mortality*: Death (all cause) before one year of life.
 - *Under-5 mortality*: Death (all cause) before 5 years of life.

2.4 Meteorological data

Hourly ERA5 reanalysis data, which is a combination of observations and mathematical models to create global coverage for meteorological data, were obtained from the Copernicus Climate Data Store for the variables of 2m temperature (air temperature), 2m dew point temperature, 10m u component of wind, 10m v component of wind and 5 radiation variables: *surface solar radiation downwards*, *surface net solar radiation*, *surface thermal radiation downwards*, *total sky direct solar radiation at surface* and *surface net thermal radiation*. This data is on a 0.25x0.25 grid and obtained for 1991-2022. To consider air pollution, reanalysis data provided by the CAMS data store maintained by the European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) is obtained for the variables of: *ozone*, *particulate matter (<1, <10 and <2.5)* and *nitrogen dioxide*. This data is on a 0.75x0.75 grid and obtained for 2003 to end of 2022. Finally, all data is aggregated to a daily minimum, maximum and mean temporal scale.

The exposures that will be explored include daily maximum, minimum and mean temperature, apparent temperature, universal thermal climate index (UTCI) and wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT). Other exposures to be explored include relative humidity and diurnal temperature range (i.e. daily maximum minus minimum temperature). In collaboration with ECMWF, wind speed and the heat stress indices of apparent temperature, heat index, UTCI, WBGT, and surface relative humidity were created using the methodology described in the *thermofeel* python library.

2.5 Data processing and analyses

All data processing and analyses will be conducted using R (version 4.1.1 or later), facilitated by RStudio, or Python (version 3.8).

Exposures will be assigned to each woman or infant in each dataset by time (e.g. date of health event, delivery, conception) and place (residential address or location of birthing facility).

2.5.1 Epidemiological analyses

Advanced regression techniques will be used to fulfil our research objectives, including time-series analysis, time-to-event analysis, conditional logistic regression, quantile regression, and machine learning methodologies.

In time-series analysis, outcomes will be aggregated to daily counts. Conditional quasi-Poisson or negative binomial regression will be used, depending on the degree of overdispersion commonly seen in such data. In the event that negative binomial models do not account for the overdispersion (due to many days with 0 outcomes), we will use zero-inflated Poisson or negative binomial models. Spline terms will be used to adjust for season and long-term trends. Cross-basis functions will be used to characterise the nonlinear and delayed effects of temperature following a distributed lag nonlinear model (DLNM) framework.

Time-to-event analysis will be used when there is censoring in the data, when the time-to-event is an outcome of interest (e.g. gestational age at diagnosis of preeclampsia), and/or when it is important to control for gestational age (e.g. for preterm birth, the likelihood of an outcome increases as gestational age increases from 22 to 36 weeks (de Bont et al., 2022)). We will fit Cox proportional hazards models with gestational age as the timescale (Schifano et al., 2016), and combine with DLNMs to capture any nonlinear or delayed effects of heat exposure. Frailty terms will account for clustering in the data. Models will adjust for individual risk factors (e.g. maternal age) as well as time-varying factors (e.g. season, humidity).

We will use a time-stratified case-crossover design when there is limited data on individual-level confounders and when we hypothesise an acute effect of heat on the outcome of interest. Here, a person's exposure levels on the day of the health event ("case day") is compared with that same person's exposure levels on proximate days when the health event did not occur ("control days"), thereby implicitly controlling for confounding factors that are fixed (or vary slowly) over time (Lu and Zeger, 2006, Tobias A et al., 2014). Control days will be selected following the time-stratified strategy: For each case, controls will be defined as the same day of the week within the same month and year (providing 3-4 controls per case). We will combine conditional logistic regression (strata, woman ID) with DLNMs to capture nonlinear and delayed effects of temperature and extreme heat (up to 6 days before the health outcome).

We will use quantile regression when the outcome of interest is a continuous measure, e.g. gestational age at delivery in completed weeks, or birth weight in grams. Here, we will estimate the effect of high ambient temperature and extreme heat on specific quantiles of the continuous outcome distribution. The specific quantiles will be based on the cut-off points that are used to define the adverse outcome, or categories of that adverse outcome, e.g. preterm birth categories (at 28, 32, and 37 weeks of gestation) or low birth weight categories (at 1000, 1500 and 2500 grams).

We will explore the influence of high temperature and extreme heat at different time periods (or lags) preceding the event. This approach reflects the potential biological pathways through which temperature can influence MNCH outcomes, where, for example, exposure to extreme heat at week 32 of pregnancy may result in a preterm birth on that same day or, more commonly, a few days thereafter. The lag structure in our models will be based on existing evidence for each temperature-outcome relationship, where possible. For example, our previous findings from South Africa show that high temperatures in early pregnancy (2-5

weeks' gestation) are associated with an increased risk of severe hypertensive disorders (Part et al., 2022).

Further, we will employ the use of machine learning modelling to explore the influence of high temperature and extreme heat on health outcomes, including the possibility to include lag times. This approach has been used in previous studies across the health field (Wiemken and Kelley, 2020). For example, a study that compared machine learning methodology to logistic regression for predicting preeclampsia as an outcome found multiple machine learning models to outperform the traditional approach (Zheng et al., 2022). A UK cohort study also used machine learning to assess what health and socio-economic factors are the most important in predicting preterm birth (Waynforth, 2022). Types of models that will be used here include methods from both regression and classification such as Convolutional Neural Nets (CNNs), Gradient Descent, Random Forests and Bayesian.

2.5.2 Subgroup analyses

We will conduct a series of subgroup analyses to characterise those women and children at greatest risk of adverse heat effects. Findings will inform the personalised early warning system. As the data allow, we will stratify by maternal characteristics (e.g. age at delivery, parity, socioeconomic status, education level, BMI, smoking), comorbidities (e.g. diabetes, HIV, chronic hypertension), infant characteristics (e.g. sex, birth weight categories). Where there is insufficient power due to small population size within sub-groups, we will test for interaction effects (temperature and maternal/infant characteristics) on the outcome of interest. Where possible, we will also stratify by region and birthing facility type (e.g. tertiary referral hospital, midwife-led clinic).

2.5.3 Pooling temperature effects

Country-specific effects (coefficients and standard errors) will be meta-analysed using the inverse variance method. Fixed-effects and random-effects will be applied using restricted maximum likelihood to estimate between-region variance and Q-profile to estimate 95% confidence intervals.

3 Data management

With the exception of data from South Africa and Kenya, which will be analysed at LSHTM respectively UNI GRAZ following a Data Sharing Agreement, each site will analyse their respective country data according to the analyses plan generated by the core statistical team. Data will be compared across countries when considered valid, but data will NOT be pooled. Data management will be carried out in accordance with the HIGH Horizons Data Management Plan, dated 30 November 2022. In accordance with this plan, our data management has the following characteristics:

- Each partner will store the data on its institutional network, on a secure server protected by two-level authentication.
- Data storage on local devices will be avoided at all times. If storing a copy of the data on local machines is necessary (e.g., the study statistician), then the data will be password-protected and only include de-identified data.
- Access to data will be restricted to a limited number of study staff that have appropriate training to manage data.
- Non-personal data (e.g., environmental or ambient temperature data) will be made openly available unless sourced from a commercial source.
- Data ownership will be with the country teams in South Africa, Kenya, Greece, Italy, and Sweden or relevant Data Sharing Agreements will be put in place.

- All data will be stored in accordance with GDPR legislation and recognised data security standards for a minimum number of years according to each country's requirements.

4 Dissemination and communication of findings

The preliminary findings from this population-level heat-health impacts study will be reported in Deliverable 2.3 'Heat-health analysis report from Italian, Swedish and African data 1', due end of November 2023. The findings related to all objectives will be reported in Deliverable D2.4 'Heat-health analysis report from Italian, Swedish and African data 2', due end of August 2025.

The results of will inform other tasks within the HIGH Horizons project:

- The results from primary objective 1 will inform the WHO Expert Group on Indicators and the development of heat-related indicators for monitoring and surveillance purposes;
- The findings from primary objectives 2 and 3 will inform the Early Warning System.

5 Ethical considerations

This study encompasses analyses of data that have already been collected in the aforementioned countries. Data will be accessed and used in accordance with the agreed design of the study, requirements of the data providers, and in compliance with legal, ethical, regulatory, funding body, and institutional requirements. Before data are shared for analyses, they will undergo anonymisation appropriate to the needs of the study. No case report forms, treatment records, or files linking participant ID codes with participant names will be shared.

The datasets will be saved using a file compression application, which allows the data to be password-protected. The data will then be shared using a time-limited, password-protected online file sharing service. In the event that data must be analysed on a local device, data files will be encrypted and temporarily stored on a password-protected computer, in accordance with the requirements specified by the data providers, to ensure confidentiality of participant information and to protect against data loss and corruption. Once data have been analysed, they will be permanently removed from the device.

No individuals will be identifiable from any publications or reports produced from this study. Results will be presented on an aggregated level only.

Obtaining informed written consent from participants is not feasible. We will therefore request a waiver of informed consent on the basis that: (i) the proposed study presents no more than minimal risk to participants; (ii) no participant will be identifiable from any reports or publications produced from the proposed study; and (iii) this study, which aims to reduce the impacts of climate change on MNCH, is not feasible without a waiver of consent.

All participating sites will obtain approval from relevant **local ethics committees**:

- For South Africa: University of the Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee;
- For analysis of South African data by LSHTM: LSHTM Observational Research Ethics Committee (UK);
- For Greece: Research Ethics Committee (University of Thessaly, Greece);
- For Italy, data access and usage are regulated by regional and national laws. DEP-Lazio is entitled to use and analyse data for epidemiological purposes (being part of its institutional mandate) but it is not allowed to share any individual data;
- For Sweden: National Ethical Review Committee (Etikprövningsmyndigheten) in Sweden;

- For Kenya: Aga Khan University Research Ethics Committee;
- For analysis of Kenyan data by UNI Graz: Research Ethics Committee (University of Graz, Austria).

6 Timeline

	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025
Protocol development								
SCC and ethical approvals								
Data sharing								
Data preparation								
Analyses								
Write up								

7 References

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